



Parent plasmid: pPtPuc3 (<https://www.addgene.org/62863/>)

Vector backbone: pUC19

PmH4p, *P. multistriata* H4 gene promoter; PtLhcf1t, *P. tricornutum* Lhcf1 gene terminator.

This plasmid is suitable for *P. multistriata* transformation through *E. coli* conjugation, contains ShBle cassette for selection and it is possible to insert an additional expression cassette (overexpression, silencing, fluorescent tag) for a gene of interest.